

Synthesis of New Local Anaesthetics. Part IV*

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Diethylaminoacetyl-2-amino-, -4-methyl-, -5-methyl-, -6-methyl-, -6-chloro-, -6-methoxy-, and -6-ethoxy-benzothiazoles and their hydrochlorides have been synthesised and their local anaesthetic activity has been tested. The pharmacological screening has shown that the hydrochloride of diethylaminoacetyl-2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole is the most active of all the compounds described here and diethylaminoacetyl-2-amino-6-methylbenzothiazole is the most active amongst the three methyl derivatives.

Hugershoff (*Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 3121) prepared 2-aminobenzothiazoles, by the action of liquid bromine on asymmetrical phenylthiourea in chloroform. Brewster and Dains (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1364) prepared several thiazoles by the cupric thiocyanate method and found that thiocyanation did not occur in compounds containing acetamido or ethoxycarbonylamino groups. In continuation of the previous work on 2-aminobenzothiazoles by Bhargava *et al.* (*this Journal*, 1958, **35**, 807; 1960, **37**, 314), it was therefore considered worthwhile, in view of their medicinal importance as local anaesthetics, to prepare 2-aminobenzothiazole, 2-amino-4-methyl-, -5-methyl-, -6-methyl-, -6-chloro-, -6-methoxy-, and -6-ethoxy-benzothiazoles and to convert these respectively into diethylaminoacetyl-2-amino-, -4-methyl-, -5-methyl-, -6-methyl-, -6-chloro-, -6-methoxy-, and -6-ethoxy-benzothiazoles, firstly by condensation with chloroacetyl chloride and secondly with diethylamine. The hydrochlorides of these bases have been prepared and their local anaesthetic activity has been tested.

A study of the pharmacological screening shows that the hydrochloride of diethylaminoacetyl-2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole is the most active of these compounds, confirming thereby that a chlorine atom in *para* position in the benzene nucleus confers more activity on the compound than the presence of a higher aromatic nucleus. (Bhargava *et al.*, *ibid.* 1960, **37**, 241). Further, it is proved that diethylaminoacetyl-2-amino-6-methylbenzothiazole is the most potent compound amongst the methyl derivatives prepared.

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E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-Aminobenzothiazoles were prepared according to the procedure of Hegershoff (*loc. cit.*). Analytical data of the compounds are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

*Compounds.	%Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1. A-B	75	129°	C ₇ H ₆ N ₂ S	20.70	21.33
2. A-4-methyl-B	70	136°	C ₈ H ₈ N ₂ S	19.30	19.51
3. A-5-methyl-B	72	143 ^b	C ₈ H ₈ N ₂ S	19.24	19.51
4. A-6-methyl-B	75	138°	C ₈ H ₈ N ₂ S	19.09	19.51
5. A-6-chloro-B	70	198°	C ₇ H ₅ N ₂ ClS	17.02	17.34
6. A-6-methoxy-B	69	146°	C ₈ H ₈ ON ₂ S	17.32	17.77
7. A-6-ethoxy-B	74	174°	C ₉ H ₁₀ ON ₂ S	16.06	16.49

* B denotes benzothiazole. A denotes 2-amino-

Chloroacetyl-2-aminobenzothiazole.—Freshly distilled chloroacetyl chloride (3.0 c.c.), dissolved in pure benzene (10 c.c.), was gradually added to 2-aminobenzothiazole (5.0 g.), dissolved in benzene (35 c.c.). The reaction mixture was warmed at 70° on a water bath for 1½ hours. Benzene was distilled; the residue was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and finally dried. The product was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 156°, yield 4.8 g.

Chloroacetyl derivatives of other 2-aminobenzothiazoles were similarly prepared. Analytical data are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Compounds.	%Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1. Chloroacetyl-A-B	60	156°	C ₉ H ₇ ON ₂ ClS	13.95	14.13
2. Chloroacetyl-A-4-methyl-B	70	180°	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₂ ClS	13.01	13.30
3. Chloroacetyl-A-5-methyl-B	82	185°	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₂ ClS	12.98	13.30
4. Chloroacetyl-A-6-methyl-B	75	183°	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₂ ClS	13.00	13.30
5. Chloroacetyl-A-6-chloro-B	68	202°	C ₉ H ₆ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	12.02	12.26
6. Chloroacetyl-A-6-methoxy-B	70	155°	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	12.35	12.47
7. Chloroacetyl-A-6-ethoxy-B	72	166°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	11.58	11.85

Diethylaminoacetyl-2-aminobenzothiazole.—To chloroacetyl-2-aminobenzothiazole (5 g.), dissolved in ethanol (50 c.c.), diethylamine (3.5 c.c.) was added; the mixture was refluxed for 3 hours. After the reaction, excess of ethanol and diethylamine were recovered by distillation and

the residue was washed with sodium bicarbonate to remove the acid impurities, and finally with water. The product was crystallised from ethanol and recrystallised from benzene in grey form, m.p. 120°.

Diethylaminoacetyl derivatives of the other 2-aminobenzothiazoles were similarly prepared. Their hydrochlorides were also prepared as usual and crystallised from ethanol-ether mixture (1 : 1). Analytical data are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

*Compounds.	Diethylaminoacetyl-2-aminobenzothiazole.				Hydrochlorides.		
	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		M.P.	%Chlorine.	
			Found.	Calc.		Found.	Calc.
1.	120°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ ON ₂ S	11.98	12.16	166°	11.76	11.85
2.	160°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ ON ₂ S	11.36	11.55	210°	11.00	11.32
3.	154°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ ON ₂ S	11.62	11.55	200°	11.08	11.32
4.	145°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ ON ₂ S	11.46	11.55	150°	11.48	11.32
5.	175°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ON ₂ ClS	10.78	10.75	220°	21.02	21.25
6.	185°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.02	10.92	230°	10.68	10.77
7.	170°	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.56	10.42	235°	10.26	10.33

* The number corresponds to those in Table II.

Pharmacological Test : Plexus Anaesthesia in Frogs.—Hydrochloride solutions (0.1% and 0.2%) were used and the time of onset of anaesthesia was recorded and compared with that of procaine hydrochloride as a standard substance. The results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Hydrochloride of diethylaminoacetyl-	With 0.1% solution for onset of anaesthesia in		With 0.2% solution for onset of anaesthesia in	
	0.05N-HCl.	0.1N-HCl.	0.05N-HCl.	0.1N-HCl.
1. *Procaine hydrochloride	10 mins.	16 mins.	7 mins.	14 mins.
2. -A-B	19	22	16	19
3. -A-4-methyl-B	14	21	12	18
4. -A-5-methyl-B	12	17	10	15
5. -A-6-methyl-B	10	26	7	12
6. -A-6-chloro-B	6	8	4	6
7. -A-6-methoxy-B	12	18	11	16
8. -A-6-ethoxy-B	11	16	9	14

* It was used as such and not in the form of diethylamino derivative.

The study of pharmacological screening has shown that the hydrochloride of diethylamino-acetyl-2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole is the most active of all the compounds and diethylamino-acetyl-2-amino-6-methylbenzothiazole is the most potent amongst the three methyl-substituted derivatives described here.

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